

Significant improvements in wear and friction of epoxy composites filled with graphene nanoplatelets and wax-containing microcapsules

Abolhassan Imani^{ab}, Hui Zhang^a, Jun Zhao^a, Jinglei Yang^c, Mohammad Owais^{ab} and Zhong Zhang^{a*}

^aCAS Key Laboratory of Nanosystem and Hierarchical Fabrication, National Center for Nanoscience and Technology, Beijing 100190, China

^b University of Chinese Academy of Science, Beijing 100049, China

^c Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Clear Water Bay, Kowloon, Hong Kong, China
(* E-mail: zhong.zhang@nanoctr.cn)

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Abstract

The mechanical and tribological properties of epoxy composites with graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) and microcapsules containing lubricant wax (WMCs) were investigated. The results showed that thermal conductivity, hardness, specific wear rate and coefficient of the friction of the nanocomposites were improved proportionally by the addition of GNP. Moreover, the incorporation of WMC to GNP/epoxy nanocomposites leads to dramatically decrease in the coefficient of friction and the specific wear rate. During wear tests, the WMCs were damaged by the severity of the counterface, releasing the wax to the contact area caused the formation of thin transfer film. Therefore it caused a significant reduction in specific wear rate and COF.

1. Introduction

Polymer composites filled with solid or liquid lubricants have been frequently applied for wear and friction applications. The solid lubricants, such as graphite, graphene nanoplatelet and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), can reduce the wear rate of polymer composites by the formation of transfer films, which are able to reduce the adhesion between polymers and counterparts [1-7]. Generally, the liquid lubricants result in lowered wear rates and coefficient of friction (COF) more significantly [8-11], compared to the solid ones.

However, it should be noted that external lubrication at the contact area may limit application of the materials [9-11] besides the fact that method is not applicable to some composites polymer. In view of these, incorporation of microencapsulated lubricant wax into polymeric matrices would be a solution. In view of these, some works [12-19] provide a solution to the above problem by incorporating of liquid lubricant containing microcapsules into the polymers.

For the first time in this work, the incorporation of two types of solid lubricants (GNP and WMC) were investigated.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials and preparation

In this research GNP with an average particle size of ~5 μm and ~15nm thickness, TiO_2 particles with ~300 nm and WMC with around ~300 μm diameter were used. The mixture of epoxy and GNP with different weight content were stirred and then use three roll milling to reach a homogeneous state. After degassing, the trapped air bubbles were removed. The curing agent MHHPA, with 1 wt % accelerator, BDMA, was then added into the epoxy mixture in a stoichiometric ratio and heated on an oil bath at 60 °C. The mixture was then mechanically stirred before it was degassed in a vacuum oven. Afterward, WMC added inside the mixture and then it was poured into a preheated steel mould and thermo-cured in an oven.

2.2 Mechanical and tribological test

Friction and wear behaviors of the samples were measured with universal tribometer (UMT-3, Bruker Corporation) under dry sliding condition through a ball-on-disc configuration. The ball was made of 302 stainless steel with a diameter of 4.0 mm and a surface roughness, Ra, of 90 nm, hardness of HRC 39. Before the wear tests, the specimens were polished with grit papers (No.1500). The wear mechanisms, as well as the tribological role of nanoparticles, were investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). DSC and DMA used for measuring T_g and storage modulus of samples, respectively.

3. Results and discussion

As shown in Fig.1 thermal conductivity of samples increases by the addition of different amounts of GNP, especially in the case of adding 10wt. %, the increment is about 93%. Fig. 2 indicates that melting point of WMC is around 35 °C and by addition of GNP it decreased slightly. By sliding the ball on the surface during the test, the temperature increases as shown in Fig. 3. Herein, the addition of GNP is supposed to be the reason to transmit the temperature to WMC causing the wax inside the capsules to melt. Fig. 4 shows the wear rate of epoxy composites is reduced by adding GNP. The best result is achieved with 10 wt.% of GNP at 0.12m/s sliding velocity, and 4N normal force for 3 hours. By continuing the addition of WMC and GNP/epoxy composites, the specific wear rate and COF decreased dramatically. Fig. 4 demonstrates the improvement in specific wear rate and

COF by adding different amounts of fillers. Fig. 5 shows the worn surface of samples after the 3 hours test. It is clearly obvious that worn surface of neat epoxy is turned rough with flaky areas, whereas the worn surface of epoxy with 10wt.% GNP and 10wt.% WMC remained smooth without any obvious damage.

Fig.1 Thermal conductivity of samples with different content of GNP

Fig. 2 The DSC curves of neat epoxy and neat WMC and epoxy with 10wt.% of WMC with and without 10wt.% GNP.

Fig. 3 Infrared image of temperature distribution on the sample surface during the test. (4N normal force and 0.12 m/s sliding velocity)

Fig. 4 Specific wear rate and frictional coefficient of epoxy with different content of GNP and WMC

Fig. 5 worn surfaces of samples after 3h wear test (a) neat epoxy, (b) epoxy with 10wt.% GNP and (c) epoxy with 10wt.% GNP & 10wt.% WMC.

4. Conclusion

Addition of GNP improved the thermal conductivity of epoxy matrix (around 93%) and also developed high quality transfer films on surface of ball during the test, were proposed to be responsible for the decreasing the specific wear rate, and COF. Addition of WMC reduced the specific wear rate and COF dramatically. Incorporating these two types of solid lubricants lead to a drastic reduction of specific wear rate and COF of epoxy composite. This is probably due to the formation of the high quality transfer film, increasing the hardness of samples by addition of GNP with epoxy matrix and also improvement of thermal conductivity of samples (fig.2) that caused melting and releasing the wax inside the micro capsules that were damaged, to the contact area. The best results were achieved by cooperation of 10wt.% WMC and 10wt.% GNP, bringing about 99% and 87% decrease in specific wear rate and COF, respectively, in comparison with the those of the neat epoxy.

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